

Flapping-Wing Flying Robot with Integrated Dual-Arm Scissors-Type Flora Sampling System

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Abstract—The flapping-wing robotic birds were inspired by nature to present an alternative way of thrust and lift generation instead of conventional high-speed rotary propellers in unmanned aerial platforms. The advances in flapping technology recently led to the prototyping of leg-claw mechanisms for perching and occasionally very lightweight arms for sampling or tiny object aerial manipulation. A dual-arm manipulator on top of a robotic bird might not be bio-inspired and safe in case of a collision with the environment or human-robot interaction. Here in this work, the previously designed dual-arm scissors-type manipulator has been improved in terms of workspace, mechanism, vision system, and blade placement to present a more natural way of sampling. The new dual-arm, with 100.2(g) weight, is redesigned inside a beak to have protection against possible collisions and also secure the cutting blades within a protected shield. During the flight, the dual-arm system is inside the cover and invisible; the lower beak is opened before manipulation and sets out the arm in a proper place for sampling. This new safety cover (beak) along with the new blade mechanism enhanced the cutting power and the safety of the operation. The experimental results show the successful cutting of a series of plant samples.

Keywords: Flapping-wing flying robot (FWFR), Scissors-type manipulator, Aerial robotics, Aerial manipulation, Dual arm.

I. INTRODUCTION

Flying with flapping-wing robots is getting more popular for experimentation, employing manual [1]–[3], or closed-loop controlled flight [4]–[8]. The continuous growth in usage of flapping-wing flying robots (FWFRs) provides the possibility of a wide variety of applications such as monitoring [9], photography, inspection [10], tiny object transportation, sampling [11], [12], among others. The controlled flight is the primary item for employing the FWFR for the mentioned applications. The flight controller ranges from linear proportional-integral-derivative (PID) designs [13], and linear quadratic regulators [14], to nonlinear methods [6]. Flight control is linked to any application derived from flapping-wing technology since the robot must carry the additional weight of the payload which could be a camera, manipulator, sensor, etc. The focus of this current work is on one particular application of the FWFR, sampling utilizing dual-arm manipulation. The manipulation is performed as a

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Fig. 1. Proposed dual-arm manipulator extended once the beak was opened. The zoomed view is shown on the left-down corner of the image and the installed camera inside the beak is shown on the right-up corner as well.

post-perching activity when the robot is in a stable position or a fixed place [15], [16].

Dual arm manipulation presents more dexterity, payload, and possibility of interaction between the arms to fulfill complex tasks. The workspace of the manipulators is shared and they must avoid any internal collisions in operation. Long et al. presented a rapidly exploring random tree method for trajectory tracking of the manipulators [17]. A modified artificial potential field was used to address this problem for two cooperative manipulators [18]. In addition to complex collision and obstacle avoidance methods, mechanical design could present a safe range of motion for the arms. Here in this work, two planar robots were designed, and setting them in different planes, the chance of the collision of the gripper with the scissors was removed. Of course, the design of the dual-arm manipulator must comply with the strict requirements of ornithopters including payload and mass distribution constraints. Animals often rely on various types of perception information to grasp and manipulate objects. Vision helps them identify and locate objects in their surroundings, which is critical for successful grasping. Dexterous animals, such as primates and birds of prey, utilize the slight differences in images between two eyes to accurately estimate target positions. In the field of lightweight aerial manipulation, stereo, and RGB-D systems are mainly used, e.g. [19], [20] or [12]. However, some species, including birds, rely on monocular inputs for spatial positioning. Inspired by this, our onboard vision system is designed to detect vegetation samples using a monocular camera. This approach minimizes weight and computational cost and avoids inaccuracies from depth sensors produced by

Fig. 2. The application of scissors manipulator in cooperative operation with another bird, perched on a branch in front of the dual arm system.

short baselines, lighting problems, or unreliable estimation in close-range scenarios. Although some work such as [21], [22] use markers to facilitate grasping with a monocular camera, our system is designed to operate in uncontrolled cluttered scenarios without markers or any other adaptation of the environment.

Lightweight manipulation, single arm [23]–[27], dual arm [28], [29], or parallel arms [30], is an interesting topic in aerial robotics using multi-rotor platforms. The range of the manipulation for multirotor systems depends on the payload of the drone, conventional systems use arms up to approximately 3(kg). This range will drop to less than 150(g) for flapping-wing robots due to the limited payload of these platforms [11], [12]. The previous dual-arm scissors-type robot had 94.1(g) mass [12]. The new dual-arm manipulator presented in this paper (see Fig. 1) fulfills the weight requirement and also includes significant design and operational improvements: i) increases the cutting power to enlarge the range of flora it can sample, ii) dual-arm re-design to improve the workspace of the system to facilitate manipulation tasks, iii) a new vision of detection system, more robust and reliable, and iv) design with a cover (similar to a bird’s beak) that protects the manipulator and that also improves the FWFR aerodynamic properties. The aerial manipulation robot has been validated in flora sampling tasks also including cooperative manipulation with two robotic birds, see Fig. 2.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows. Section II deals with the integration of flight with perching and manipulation. Section III presents the design and configuration of the dual-arm scissors-type robot. The opening/closing mechanism sequence is expressed in Section IV. The vision detection system is presented in Section V. The integration with the robot bird and some experimental validation results are provided in Section VI. The concluding remarks are stated in Section VII.

II. FLIGHT, PERCHING, AND MANIPULATION

Flapping wing robots with perching and manipulation capabilities were recently designed and developed in the GRIFFIN¹ project. The main challenges of these systems

¹<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/788247>

Fig. 3. The schematic of the flying bird with a conventional manipulator on the branch after perching. The active leg can shift the workspace of the robot.

are represented by the following stages: (1) the accuracy of the approaching flight, (2) the accuracy in position and orientation of the perching; (3) the spent energy in the perching, (4) the stability after perching despite the motion and forces of the manipulators, and (5) the manipulator reach and dexterity.

We have previously designed and developed claws to absorb/dissipate, and eventually store, the energy when perching on a branch [4] and to maintain stability. Figure 2 shows a perched bird with a claw holding the bird’s weight to maintain stability and a conventional manipulator on top of the bird. Methods to maintain dynamic stability while manipulating have also been researched [31]. They are not the subject of this paper. On the right, the new flapping wing system with the manipulator inside the beak is shown.

The manipulation workspace of the perched robotic bird mainly depends on stages (1), (2), and (5), mentioned at the beginning of this section. Notice that oscillations in the approaching flight induced by the flapping-wing motion make the perching more difficult. It is also possible to switch from flapping to gliding before the perching. In our bird, the precision of the flight in height should be less than 15 cm to perch successfully on a branch. This error can be compensated by an active leg (see leg with a joint and the claw in the perched bird at the left in Fig. 2) facilitating the perching as described in [4]. We have also increased the repeatability as described in [32]. The weight of the manipulator should be as small as possible because increasing the payload has a very negative impact on the controllability of the approach trajectory and then on the accuracy of stages (1) and (2). More specifically, because the flapping wings are unable to generate sufficient lift and thrust to compensate for the excessive added weight.

After perching, the joint in the leg can change the orientation of the bird, see Fig. 3. The body control system after perching to extend the workspace for manipulation was presented in [33]. Then, the only component required to have the flora sampling system is a new manipulation system based on a dual-arm scissor instead of the conventional manipulator on top of the perched bird shown at the left in Fig. 2. Furthermore, the crashes in the perching can cause mechanical deformations and particularly misalignment in the scissors. Thus, this paper presents a new dual-arm manipulator inside the beak to protect the manipulator as shown in Fig. 1 and at the right of Fig. 2. The manipulator design to obtain the required reach and dexterity to perform the sampling of stems and leaves is the subject of Section

Fig. 4. The exploded view of the opening and closing mechanism.

III.

III. MECHANICAL DESIGN

The new dual-arm manipulator was designed to solve the main lacks identified in the previous version while meeting the weight requirements to enable stable and high-maneuverability flapping-wing flight. To increase the cutting power of the scissor dual-arm manipulator, the servomotor changed to a slightly bigger size in comparison with the previous dual-arm manipulator [12]. Another objective of the new design is to protect the manipulators and put them inside a beak-like shape to secure the cutting blades. Hence, the base position of the first motors of the left and right arms has been modified to occupy less space. The links have been designed as short as possible so that they do not collide with each other in opening and closing motions. The servomotors have been arranged so that the heads point in the same direction, which reduces the space occupied by the manipulator in its optimal position. The beak opening mechanism consists of two gears, one of them being integrated into the lower part of the beak, and the other connected to the servomotor that performs the opening/closing movement of the beak, and it is fixed to the bird's frame Fig. 4. The gear of the lower part of the beak has been made as large as possible so that the servomotor suffers less from the generated torque by the weight of the entire manipulator as well as the lower part of the beak. Two walls have been added to the sides of the driving gear since due to the asymmetry of the beak and the manipulator, a torsion is produced that displaces the gears, these walls are necessary to keep them together. In addition, the servomotor is capable of performing the opening and closing movements. The axes of the gears come to separate, which is why a fastener has been used to hold them together so that the teeth of the pick gear do not jump into those of the directing gear.

The beak has been made of two different materials. The upper part is printed using Thermoplastic polyurethane (TPU) due to its weight and elasticity since this allows withstanding an impact without breaking in the event of a fall. This also serves as a soft coverage to safely interact with humans/environment in terms of possible collisions. The lower part of the beak is made of polylactic acid (PLA) to

Fig. 5. Coordinates system for each link of both arms and global reference.

have enough rigidity to ensure the stability of the manipulator while it performs tasks for which precision will generally be required. This material has also been used to make one of the fastenings for the blades and one of the parts that make up the clamp. Carbon fiber has been used for the joints between the different links, as it provides rigidity and is quite lightweight. As mentioned previously, once the servomotor was selected, the manipulator had to be made in such a way that it occupied as little space as possible while remaining inside the beak, to make the beak as small as possible and save weight, and still making the design bio-inspired by the actual beak of a bald eagle. Since the bird's weight is critical for it to fly, reducing the weight has been considered a priority over improving other characteristics of the manipulator.

The new design, see Fig. 5, has a significantly larger dual-arm working space than the old version. As can be seen in Fig. 6, for this configuration of the manipulator, a workspace that covers approximately $85(\text{cm}^2)$ has been achieved for the right arm, which will be the one that grabs the stem, so that even if there is an error in the bird's perch, the manipulator has room to adapt to the perching conditions.

The workspace design (the $85(\text{cm}^2)$ area) was indirectly defined by the allowable weight for the dual arm system, approximately predefined $100(\text{g})$. The allowable weight defined the beak size (the design of the protective cover), the beak geometry defined the size of the motors and links to fit inside, and finally, the size of the links defined the workspace. In summary, the workspace is the result of the following sequence in design: allowable weight \rightarrow beak size \rightarrow link design \rightarrow workspace sizing $85(\text{cm}^2)$.

IV. OPENING/CLOSING/CUTTING SEQUENCE

The arrangement of six motors, a gripper, and scissors inside a small beak is a challenge. There is a specific configuration that can hold the system inside the protection cover. Hence, a particular set of motions is used to bring out the manipulators for operation and later put them back inside. The sequence of movements is programmed with a state machine with the following stages:

(1) *Rest position*: All the servos are placed in their rest position so that the manipulator can fit inside the beak.

Fig. 6. The workspace of the dual-arm manipulator; left arm's workspace, right one and both common domain of operation.

Fig. 7. The comparison of the old and new scissors-type manipulators; using the two blades on the scissors arm is noticeable in the new version (right manipulator in the picture). Considering the 32.8(g) 3D printed servo holder of the new system, it presented the weight of the arm 100.2(g).

(2) *Beak opening*: The beak opens without making any movement with the manipulator. The time of the opening is adjustable. Once the beak is open, after a pause of two seconds, the system is ready for opening the arms.

(3) *Manipulator opening*: All the manipulator servos move progressively until they adopt a defined final position. After a pause of 2 seconds, it is ready to start the operation. The pause duration is adjustable; it gives the vision system enough time to detect the stem and send the cutting coordinates to the manipulator.

(4) *Manipulator operation*: In order to increase the working space of the manipulator, while the scissors arm remains stationary, the gripper arm moves to the cutting position determined by the vision system, see Section V. Then, the gripper will close to hold the target element and, after a delay of one second, the gripper arm will move to a certain position defined on the axis of symmetry between the two arms, inside the shared workspace of both arms. When it has reached the position, the scissors arm, which remained still, will move until it reaches the cutting point, and then the blades will close at the maximum speed allowed by the internal control of the servomotor. After another second the blades open, leaving the cut element held with the gripper.

(5) *Manipulator closing*: The manipulator adopts the initial rest position, that can be set inside the beak. It is first necessary to move arms away from each other. The scissors are then opened enough for the manipulator to adopt the rest position (within the beak). After reaching this position, and with the stem held inside the beak, we move to “beak closing” state.

(6) *Beak closing*: To conclude, the beak is closed, only

exchanging the final and initial positions.

V. VISION DETECTION SYSTEM

Most animals rely on vision to grasp and manipulate objects. Vision helps animals identify and locate objects in their environment, which is crucial for successful grasping [34]. In fact, animals with dexterous limbs have the brain areas responsible for visual processing (e.g., primary visual cortex) heavily connected to motor areas that control grasping movements [35]. Many animals such as primates and birds of prey use stereopsis (i.e., slight differences in images between their two eyes) to estimate target position accurately. However, animals such as fish and birds can rely on monocular cues to determine the spatial positioning of objects. For instance, birds with long beaks have been shown to effectively peck and grasp even with narrow binocular fields [36]. Following a bioinspired approach, in this work we use monocular vision for the detection and localization of the samples. Using monocular vision reduces the sensor weight and computational cost and avoids the inaccuracies in the estimation of depth typical of stereo systems with short baselines, lighting problems, or unreliable estimation in close-range scenarios. The adopted vision system aims to:

- Ensure accurate and reliable detection under varying environmental conditions, e.g., lighting.
- Reduce the computational cost and processing time of the detection to enable real-time operation.
- Avoid the use of depth sensors. Relying on a depth map for our case may not be reliable since; i) the dimensions of the beak would require a very small baseline for stereo pairs, leading to poor depth accuracy; ii) RGB-D cameras are unreliable under insufficient illumination or direct sunlight which affects infrared performance; and iii) the short distance between the target and the camera lens results in inaccurate depth estimates.

The developed method processes monocular RGB images to detect the vegetation sample (target) and locates it by computing its intersection with the plane where the manipulator operates. The camera is mounted within the beak and designed with a field of view to cover the workspace of both arms. First, the target is segmented from the background using color thresholding. Let \mathbf{I}_k be the k -th processed image and C the set of selected color values. The segmented region \mathbf{S}_k , which elements are in \mathbb{Z}_2 , is defined as:

$$\mathbf{S}_k(x,y) = \frac{\alpha - 1}{\alpha^{k+1} - 1} \sum_{i=0}^k \left(\alpha^{k-i} [\mathbf{I}_i(x,y) \in C] \right), \quad (1)$$

with $0 < \alpha < 1$ and $[\cdot]$ denoting the Iverson brackets. We opted for an exponential weighted mean approach for the following reasons: i) it allows us to give more emphasis to recent observations while still considering previous ones, ii) it inherently smooths out noisy data, and iii) the computational burden is low, as the value of \mathbf{S}_k can be recursively computed from \mathbf{S}_{k-1} for $k > 0$. Note that Eq. (1) assumes that $(\alpha - 1) \sum_{i=0}^k \alpha^{k-i} = \alpha^{k+1} - 1$. Further, for higher computational efficiency, only the last $N = 30$ images are considered.

plant	name	diameter ϕ (mm), double blade	diameter ϕ (mm), single blade
	Agrostis idahoensis	up to 1.81	up to 1.32
	Tipuana Tipu	up to 2.02	up to 1.56
	Rosemary	up to 2.34	up to 1.40
	Agrostis idahoensis (dry)	up to 2.16	up to 1.36
	Pyracantha coccinea	up to 1.46	failed
sheets of paper, 0.1(mm) thickness		up to 2	failed

Fig. 8. The cutting comparison of both manipulators: the new one with two blades and the older one with one.

Next, the Hough Transform is applied to \mathbf{S}_k to detect lines. We select the best line $\mathbf{r}^* = (\rho, \theta)$ – i.e., the line with the highest number of votes – such as $|\theta| < \theta_{th}$. $\theta_{th} = 5(\text{deg})$ is selected such that only vertical lines are considered. The selected line can be easily expressed in homogeneous coordinates as $\mathbf{r}^* = [\cos \theta, \sin \theta, -\rho]^T$. As $\mathbf{r}^* \in \mathbb{P}^2$ denotes a plane in \mathbb{R}^3 , and assuming $\Pi \in \mathbb{R}^3$ is the plane where the manipulator operates (i.e., plane XY in Fig. 6), the intersection of both planes ($\mathbf{s} = \Pi \cap \mathbf{r}^*$) gives the cutting line, which includes the suitable stem cutting point. Since our vision system does not provide depth estimation, the stem cutting point (i.e., the intersection point of the stem with the manipulator workspace) is at some point of the line \mathbf{s} . During stage *Manipulator operation* in Section IV the manipulator is commanded to move along the path given by \mathbf{s} ensuring the grasping and cutting of the sample if it is within the manipulator workspace.

VI. EXPERIMENTS

The functionalities for flora sampling have been implemented on a *Raspberry PI 3B+*, selected as the main processing unit on board the ornithopter due to its strict payload requirements. They were programmed in *ROS* (Robot Operating System) with two nodes: one for the movement of the manipulator and another for the vision system. The control of the manipulator servos has been performed through the servo driver *PCA9685*. The *Raspberry* communicates via I2C with the *PCA9685* servo driver, which allows it to send, in addition to the power, the PWM signals that command the position of each servo. All the mentioned components were already part of the FWFR platform and were necessary for its correct operation, so they are not considered added weight due to the manipulator.

A third-degree polynomial has been used for interpolation to make the movement of the manipulator smooth and less aggressive for the servomotors. The four parameters that describe such a polynomial function allow us to define the initial and final positions and velocities of every movement.

A. Cutting Power Experiments

First, we present some cutting power experiments and comparisons between single and double-blade configurations. The old version of the scissors-type manipulator described in [12] used one blade on the left arm, see Fig. 7. The manipulator presented in this paper has two blades to improve the cutting power, allow cutting materials from both directions and avoid sliding of the object during the cutting. There is another drawback to the one-blade configuration; it bends very tiny samples instead of cutting. In other words, the gap between the blade and the carbon fiber plate allows the bending. However, with two blades, this problem was solved. In addition, the proposed manipulator uses a stronger servomotor with greater torque, enabling a better cutting performance. In Fig. 8 a comparison between the obtained results with both configurations for the same samples is shown. The smallest improvement in cutting occurs for the *Tipuana Tipu*, being 27.07% the increase of the cutting diameter; while the highest is given to *Rosemary*, achieving a 40.17%. For other more resistant samples such as *Pyracantha coccinea* or sheets of paper, the manipulator with a single blade is not capable of cutting.

B. Main Results

To carry out the experiment we have arranged the bird with the orientation it would have when perching on a branch. A stem has been placed on a holder, which will be the one that the manipulator cuts. A scenario with good lighting has been chosen to ensure the correct functioning of the implemented onboard perception algorithm. Also, there were no other green elements in the camera field of view that could be detected as cutting targets.

In Fig. 9, the following stages by the manipulator during the experiment are shown. First, the manipulator is in the resting position (1), inside the beak. Once the beak is opened (2), the manipulator extends outward (3). Once the vision system has detected the cutting line \mathbf{s} , the segment of \mathbf{s} within the manipulator workspace is determined and the right arm moves along that segment and grips the stem (5), so that it remains steady while the blades of the left arm cut it (6). After cutting the branch, the left arm moves (7) so that the manipulator returns to its resting position (8) and the beak can be closed (9).

Additionally, in Fig. 10, the view from the camera located inside the beak during the experiment is shown. In (a), which corresponds to image (4) in Fig. 9, the system waits to receive the signal for the manipulator to take the sample. The cutting line \mathbf{s} , seen from a camera as a point, is shown in yellow. In (b) -(5)-, the clamp is moving along \mathbf{s} , and in (c) -(6)-, the cut is made when the manipulator is extended at the direction of \mathbf{s} . Finally, in (d) -(9)-, the cut stem can be seen held inside the beak. The entire experiment was completed in 1.37(min), although, as indicated, we can define the speed at which the actuators move. Please see the *video*² representation of the experiment as supplementary

²Please check supplementary material or GRVC YouTube Channel.

Fig. 9. Images of a sampling experiment with timestamps showing the sequence of the operation. The video file of the experiment is available as supplementary material of the paper in the online version.

Fig. 10. Camera view of a vegetation sampling experiment.

material to the article in the online version. Therefore, the sequence could have been performed in less time at the cost of straining the servomotors and producing a less smooth movement. The proposed system was tested in a series of >40 experiments, achieving successful sampling in $>97\%$ of the cases. First, the accuracy of the vision system was estimated in preliminary testbench experiments. The stem was correctly detected in all cases. The error in the localization of s in the camera image plane was lower than 2 pixels, which provides significant accuracy in our sampling system since the distance between the tips of the scissor when open is 4(cm). In addition, notice that the computation of s was performed with every image while the arm is in stage *Manipulator operation*, so that the manipulator control system adapts the clamp trajectory in case the stem, bird, or the manipulator move during the operation for instance due to wind, providing additional robustness.

VII. CONCLUSIONS

This work presented an experimental investigation of a flapping aerial robotic system with dual-arm manipulation

to cut and sample stems, plants, and leaves. The dual arm system is a scissors-type arm plus another manipulator as the gripper to perform the sampling efficiently. The previous version of the system did not have protection for the blades and exposed them during the flight which is dangerous [12]. The manipulator here is redesigned inside a beak-shaped protection shield. The blades also doubled to increase the power of the cut and an enhancement in the camera design was made. All these changes improved the cutting and sampling performance of the manipulator. The results showed successful implementation of the mechatronics design and sampling in a laboratory environment. The proposed system has been experimentally validated also in cooperative operation with another bird, perched on a branch in front of the dual arm system. One of these experiments is also shown in the video³ attached as supplementary material. Future work includes the validation of the integration and flora sampling operation of the birds in experiments outdoors and in natural environments. Exploring sensor integration is suggested to enable the robot to detect failed cuts and automatically attempt multiple cuts until successful. Fully leveraging sensory feedback before resorting to heavier hardware would minimize unnecessary weight and better align with the constraints of aerial vehicle design.

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³Please check supplementary material or GRVC YouTube Channel.

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